

EPOS SP – Grant Agreement n. 871121

D2.3 - Landscape Analysis Guidelines

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V1	16/07/2020	Initial version (WP2)
V2	27/07/2020	Final version after EB revision

Table of contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Landscape Analysis Guidelines.....	6
2.1 Existing Documents.....	8
2.2 Interviews with TCS and ICS Representatives	8
2.3 Meetings with National Authorities (NACB and GA)	9
2.4 Service Provider Surveys	9
3. Data Protection.....	10
4. Conclusion	11
Annex 1 - TCS Interview Guidelines (July 2020).....	13

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.3, envisioned in WP2 Task 2.2 of the EPOS SP project, is aimed at elaborating the methodology for the Landscape Analysis to be performed within WP2 and coordinated with WP8. The document explains the objective of the Landscape Analysis and it provides the guidelines and tools that will be used to undertake this task.

The Landscape Analysis, to be delivered by M30 (July 2022), concerns the mapping and description of the EPOS Delivery Framework considered as a multidimensional space in which each dimension corresponds to a specific element determining the construction and the operation of the EPOS Research Infrastructure (RI). The Landscape Analysis is focused on the internal structure of the EPOS RI and it is aimed at understanding its functioning for creating awareness about the sustainable operation of the EPOS Delivery Framework. The Landscape Analysis will foster the elaboration and the adoption of appropriate plans by EPOS ERIC and the whole community to tackle the challenge of the long-term sustainability of the EPOS Delivery Framework. The Landscape Analysis is a dynamic action and it will be conducted with a short-term perspective in 2020 and continue with a long-term perspective in 2021 and 2022 onward. It will certainly represent an important contribution to design the full operational phase of the EPOS RI in 2022.

The achievements of the Landscape Analysis will be transferred to WP8 to be used as input to the elaboration of the EPOS Sustainability Plan, main outcome of the EPOS SP project. Therefore, the Landscape Analysis is an essential contribution for evaluating the robustness and readiness of the construction and operation of the EPOS Delivery Framework. It will be used to create knowledge, awareness and preparedness within the EPOS community for fostering a motivated contribution to these undertakings.

This deliverable presents the methodology for collecting the necessary information to conduct the Landscape Analysis. It provides guidelines for the key stakeholders that will be involved in different interactions and consultations. Specific sub-paragraphs focus on the different stakeholders. The data protection issue is also discussed.

This deliverable, the first one under EPOS SP Task 2.2 *Fostering efficient mechanisms to support EPOS Thematic Services through national nodes*, will feed a subsequent deliverable, *D2.4 Report on the Landscape Analysis on national mechanisms to support national nodes*, addressing the governance, legal and financial dimensions and concerning the national mechanisms to support national nodes.

1. Introduction

The EPOS RI has concluded its implementation phase and is currently facing the transition to the operational phase. This peculiar stage in the lifecycle of the EPOS RI, named EPOS Pilot Operational Phase (EPOS POP), is characterised by a Strategic Plan (2020-2022) with the overarching objective of building and operating the EPOS Delivery Framework (Figure 1) in a sustainable way.

Figure 1. The EPOS architecture and the Delivery Framework composed of TCS, ICS-C, ICS-D and the Executive Coordination Office (ECO). The green box represents the EPOS Delivery Framework and therefore defines the external perimeter.

The EPOS SP project timeline intentionally coincides with the EPOS POP. The EPOS SP activity plan represents a specific objective of the 2020-2022 EPOS ERIC Strategic Plan dealing with the financial viability of the EPOS Delivery Framework and contributing to tackle the challenge of the long-term sustainability of the EPOS RI.

The Landscape Analysis, envisioned in the project activity plan as a key undertaking for the governance and financial sustainability and thus connecting WP2 with WP8, has been recognised by the Executive Board of the project and by the Executive Coordination Office of EPOS ERIC as a key contribution for the operation of the EPOS RI. For this reason, it has been decided to extend the Landscape Analysis to the whole Delivery Framework containing the EPOS ERIC, the TCS and the ICS. This implies the involvement of all EPOS SP WPs (3, 4, 5 and 6) and, consequently, that the Landscape Analysis will actually contribute to the transfer of achievements from WPs 2-6 to the transversal WP8 and WP7.

The Landscape Analysis of the EPOS Delivery Framework can be depicted as a multidimensional space in which each dimension corresponds to a specific key element determining the construction and the operation of the EPOS RI. It then focuses on the internal structure of the EPOS RI and is aimed at understanding its functioning for creating awareness about the sustainable operation of the EPOS Delivery Framework. In this context, the landscape analysis in EPOS SP can be considered as a sort of organisational analysis of the mission-driven EPOS RI. We will consider at a later stage extending the Landscape Analysis to the external framework looking for EPOS collaborators worldwide rather than competitors.

The following dimensions can be considered as the key elements of the EPOS RI operation:

1. Governance
2. Financial
3. Legal
4. Technological
5. Users' environment
6. Stakeholders' environment (private sector, society)
7. Global connections.

The first four dimensions, or key elements, characterise the concept of sustainability of a RI, intended as a four-dimension vector. The other dimensions contribute to the exploitation of results. All dimensions contribute to the impact assessment. The “Global connections” is the bridge to the external world (external perimeter in Figure 1) for what concerns the collaborative frameworks and cooperation. The inclusion of users and stakeholders within the landscape is motivated by the fact that they can influence and be influenced by the way in which we are building and operating the EPOS Delivery Framework. The technological dimension has key implications on the scientific impact of the EPOS RI.

The main objective of the EPOS SP WP2 *Governance and Financial Framework* is to assess financial viability and to foster long-term sustainability of the EPOS Delivery Framework (Figure 1). To achieve long-term sustainability, it is necessary to strengthen the financial mechanisms in a governance and legal framework coherent with the EPOS ERIC guidance of the EPOS RI. Hence, it is necessary to analyse the EPOS organisational mechanisms and further investigate the current functioning of the TCS and the challenges they are facing, presently and in the future. Actions will be launched to encourage National Authorities to join EPOS ERIC (and thereby providing a membership fee) and to harmonise national funding and optimising national investments. In the context of nurturing financial and legal/governance sustainability, Task 2.2 deals more specifically with reinforcing the robustness of the in-kind contributions of the TCS through national and institutional engagement in the EPOS Delivery Framework. The Landscape Analysis will in this context identify difficulties that might weaken or hinder long-term contributions to EPOS TCS. There is a need to map the financial flow and the national mechanisms that exist for supporting Service Providers and their contributions to EPOS in the long-term. Once the landscape has been mapped and described, the next step will be to evaluate the organisation in order to identify adequate ways to address the main recognised difficulties and procedures to strengthen the link between EPOS and the research organisations participating to the EPOS integration plan. When necessary, links are made to Task 2.3 *Actions to consolidate the current EPOS Financial Plan*.

Because the objectives of Task 2.2 and Task 8.1 (*Sustainability on Data Provision and preservation*) of the EPOS SP project are closely related, the work on the Landscape Analysis guidelines has been done in collaboration by the team members of both Tasks. While Task 2.2 focuses on the TCS and Service Provider level, Task 8.1 digs deeper and concentrates on the Data Providers. Face-to-face meetings had been planned between members but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, all meetings have been carried out remotely. The impact on the deliverable is minor. Task members from WPs 2 and 8 have met by teleconference regularly during the spring of 2020 (March 24th, April 7th, April 29th, May 15th, May 20th and May 26th) and the work has continued by email.

The EPOS ERIC Executive Committee, the General Assembly and the Service Coordination Committee have been kept informed about the progress, especially since the Landscape Analysis has a strong impact on both EPOS SP and EPOS ERIC. This is also the reason for the wide scope of the target audience of the Analysis; not

only TCS including Service Providers and Data Providers, but also national governments, funding agencies and the ICS-C hosting organisations.

2. Landscape Analysis Guidelines

The objective of this deliverable is to describe the methodology and provide guidelines for collecting information to implement the Landscape Analysis.

The Landscape Analysis is carried out in a framework constrained by crucial milestones for EPOS ERIC: the establishment of the TCS, the activation of the services for their governance and coordination which implies the finalisation of the collaboration agreements in 2020, which, in turn, will formally connect the TCS to EPOS ERIC. In this context, the Governance and Coordination Services need to be refined and detailed also with respect of the work programmes linked to the allocation of resources for their execution. The Landscape Analysis is also relevant for discussing financial eligibility and the 2021-2023 Services Framework Agreement that has to be approved by the EPOS General Assembly later in 2020/early 2021. It is therefore essential to improve our understanding of the current status of the services that were proposed and validated during the EPOS IP project. To this task, it is necessary to interact with several target audiences such as TCS and ICS service providers, TCS coordinators, research organisations and national authorities. In particular, exchanges with the TCS are necessary to better understand short- and medium-term issues including the current TCS governance structure, the work programmes for 2020 and 2021-2023, and their financial status. To succeed in this series of actions, it is necessary to update the EPOS TCS Cost-Book with information that only the TCS representatives can provide. Indeed, in WP2 there is the Task 2.3 which is in charge of updating the Cost-Book and the EPOS Financial Plan and it is therefore involved in the Landscape Analysis. The Cost-Book was one of the deliverables of the EPOS IP project and it has been used as the basis for defining the EPOS financial framework. It is now essential to analyse the situation adopting a long-term perspective (2022 onward) to estimate the range of national support and adopt a strategy for reinforcing it and guarantee that it lasts over time. All relevant information collected during the interviews with the TCS representatives will also serve to update the Cost-Book.

In general, the information to be collected for the Landscape Analysis can be obtained following two approaches: i) internal, focusing on the service landscape and the different structures and bodies within EPOS; ii) external, involving national authorities and funding agencies. It is important to elaborate a strategy suitable for satisfying and complementing both perspectives, and, more specifically, for harmonising actions towards the EPOS ERIC General Assembly.

The proposed methodology to undertake the Landscape Analysis relies on collecting the necessary information:

- from existing documents
- by interviews with TCS and ICS representatives
- by meetings with national authorities (NACB and GA)
- by dedicated surveys.

By the means of these different actions we will collect relevant information to be elaborated in the short-term (2020) and in the long-term (2022 onward) to generate several analyses of the internal landscape characterising the EPOS Delivery Framework. During each action we will explore each one of the seven dimensions of the EPOS RI. For practical reasons, the short-term analysis, performed in 2020, will be focused on the first four dimensions: Governance, Financial, Legal, Technological.

The necessary information that needs to be collected in the short-term perspective includes:

- Architecture of the TCS:
 - Confirmation on the identities and the status as legal subjects of Service Providers.
 - Identification of TCS Coordinators, TCS Boards, advisory boards, etc.
 - Description of the internal and external communication structures.
 - List of data providers for each service.
- Information on services that are ready to enter the EPOS Pre-Operational Phase (POP) without additional funding from EPOS.
- Data Provision
 - Data providers at national level and at TCS level.
 - Completeness of supplier letters.
 - Robustness of the data policy.
 - Robustness of access rules.
- TCS Governance
 - Description of activities for 2020-2022.
 - Breakdown of costs to be borne by EPOS ERIC.

The short-term analysis will essentially rely on existing documents and on the interviews with TCS and ICS representatives.

In the medium and long-term perspective, it is important to collect information allowing for a better understanding of the stable funding and support from the research community towards the service providers and, in prolongation, to the TCS. To this purpose, Task 2.2 has been mandated to enquire on the range of national situations and mechanisms suitable to support EPOS services by mapping the financial flow. There is a need to get a comprehensive understanding of the existing and future financial and governance commitments from ministries, national research organisations and other funding organisations. This perspective will mostly be addressed by means of Service Provider Survey (see paragraph 2.4) through discussions with national authorities during meetings with the EPOS ERIC General Assembly and the National Authorities Consultation Board (see paragraph 2.3). Interactions with national research organisations will be conducted in agreement with TCS partners and/or National Authorities. One of the most important topics to be analysed in this context, is the long-term engagement in the provision of in-kind contributions and other resources.

Although the Landscape Analysis has a strong financial and legal/governance character, it is also important to consider technical aspects as well as aspects regarding staff and support from researchers, since they also contribute to long-term sustainability.

The Landscape Analysis, and especially its long-term perspective, is of course directly related to WP8 and the end-of-the-project deliverables. The outcomes will be used for fuelling the final report of WP8, dealing with the EPOS long-term sustainability at any level.

2.1 Existing Documents

Documents previously elaborated by the EPOS community, in particular during the EPOS IP project, will be used to collect the necessary background information for the Landscape Analysis. In particular, we will specifically take into account the documents concerning the EPOS architecture, the Governance and Financial models, the TCS Cost-Book and the TCS Consortium Agreements. The deliverables elaborated at the end of the EPOS IP project (September 2019) will be also useful for this undertaking as well as those from other EPOS related projects (such as the SERA project).

The available documents will be analysed by the teams involved in WP2 and WP8 and presented for discussion to the Executive Board. This will represent an initial picture of the legal, governance and financial frameworks that will be integrated with the technical information to set the starting conditions for the Landscape Analysis.

2.2 Interviews with TCS and ICS Representatives

Interviews with TCS Representatives

After elaborating the information extracted from existing documents, the subsequent step to be performed by WP2 and WP8 partners will be to interview TCS representatives. It is generally acknowledged that TCS are key players within the EPOS structure for the short-, medium- and long-term perspective. Task 2.2 is about strengthening the structure supporting TCS, therefore, it is reasonable to directly approach them during the Landscape Analysis. It should be noted that this is the first time that each TCS is expected to work as formal consortium.

The interviews with TCS will be conducted in two-time windows: July-August and September-October 2020. Due to the current COVID-19 pandemic, all interviews will be performed via teleconferences. The organisation of the interviews and the objectives were anticipated to TCS during the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee (SCC) meeting held on the 28th of May 2020. Follow-up information and practical details were sent out to all TCS representatives by the EPOS ERIC Management and Operation Unit of the ECO. Each TCS will be interviewed separately and it is expected that they are represented at least by the TCS Representative in the SCC, the Chair of the Consortium Board, and the Representative of the organisation in charge of the TCS Governance and Coordination service. Of course, members of Consortium Board and representatives of the service providers are encouraged to participate. TCS legal and financial experts are also welcome, if the TCS require their participation.

The interviews will cover issues related not only to Task 2.2 but also to the related tasks 2.3 (*Consolidation of the EPOS ERIC Financial Plan*) and 8.1 (*Sustainability of Data Provision and preservation*). These issues are deeply entwined so task members work jointly for a more dynamic outcome and efficient time management. Interviews with key persons of the different TCS will allow for getting a helicopter perspective of the general situation of each one of the consortia and, in detail, to grasp the readiness of operation of services. The TCS interviews will also provide information of more practical character for continuing the Landscape Analysis, for example by confirming and completing information on the Coordinator, Board, Service Providers, Data Providers, etc.

After the first round of interviews, an informal evaluation between WP2 and WP8 members will be done in order to verify that the questions and the structure are relevant and that the message gets through to TCS.

The format of the following interviews will then be adapted for an even more efficient structure in order to assure that a maximum of information is collected. The task members also prepared practical Interview Guidelines for their own use to allow for streamlined interventions (Annex 1). The interviews will also strive towards medium-term objectives. The discussions with TCS representatives will anchor the work within the TCS, allowing for explanation of the scope of the two surveys to be carried out in early 2021 and for a smooth operation of them. Further, the interviews will allow for perfecting the design and contents of the surveys and confirming the list of Service and Data Providers so that the surveys can be sent out to the target audiences.

The interview outcomes will certainly serve as valuable input to the long-term vision of the service operation and they will be integrated in the project-wide work on the sustainability of EPOS's Delivery Framework and in that regard fuel the final project deliverables.

Interviews with ICS Representatives

A series of interviews with the hosting organisations is also planned in September – October 2020 together with a few meetings with the IT Board in charge of coordinating the IT development of the TCS-ICS system. These interviews are aimed at including the Central Hub of the Integrated Core Services (ICS-C) in the Landscape Analysis taking into account the finalisation of the discussions for hosting the ICS-C. This is of relevance for the legal, governance, financial and technical dimensions of the landscape analysis. The meetings with the IT Board, which foresee the participation of ICS-C Director, ICS-C Technical and Operational Coordinators, are necessary to discuss the inclusion of the IT implementation of the EPOS Delivery Framework (that is, the TCS-ICS system) in the subsequent steps (mid- and long-term) of the Landscape Analysis.

2.3 Meetings with National Authorities (NACB and GA)

The National Authorities are already engaged in EPOS, essentially in two boards: the EPOS ERIC General Assembly, the governing body of the EPOS RI, and the National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB) envisioned in the framework of the WP2 activities of EPOS IP. The former is already established and thirteen countries are formally engaged in the EPOS ERIC GA. The latter has been established in 2020 and it includes representatives of those countries not yet engaged in EPOS ERIC. The plan is to have at least twelve countries engaged in the NACB.

The interactions with National Authorities will be planned and agreed with all WP2 partners and conducted through meetings whereas the communication flow with these two boards will be formally managed by EPOS ERIC, coordinator of the EPOS SP project and lead beneficiary of WP2.

The interactions with National Authorities will provide information to explore the financial and stakeholders' environment dimensions of the landscape analysis.

2.4 Service Provider Surveys

After the interviews with TCS and ICS representatives, a series of surveys is foreseen in the EPOS SP DoA. The expectation is to collect further information relevant to the Landscape Analysis. The surveys are actions envisioned for the mid-term and long-term perspective of the Landscape Analysis. Two rounds of surveys will be carried out: i) addressing the Service Providers on the sustainability of Service Provision in a wide scope

(in the framework of Task 2.2.); ii) addressing the Data Providers on the robustness of the Data Provision structure (in the framework of Task 8.1). It should be noted that the Data Providers surveyed through Task 8.1 shall not be limited to those already engaged in current TCS. As explained above, some of the issues to be analysed by Task 2.2 and Task 8.1 are closely connected, and therefore, the surveys have been designed jointly. The task participants decided to base their work on the Service Provider survey and then adapt it to the needs of the Data Provider survey, for easier management. The objectives of the surveys have been established by creating a list of sustainability indicators that can be properly measured. These indicators were organised according to the four-dimension grid previously described (Governance, Financial, Legal and Technological dimensions of sustainability). It is suggested to continue to survey the EPOS Service Providers every three or four years, to follow the sustainability development. Through thorough discussions between Task members, the questions that should enable the measuring of the sustainability indicators were then elaborated. Each member having a different role in EPOS SP as well as a different experience from previous EPOS work, meant that diverse approaches met and led to a fruitful process.

The outcomes of the TCS interviews will be analysed and the survey then updated to reflect the current status of Service Providers activities. It is also possible that the survey will be submitted to a small test group in the first stage, in order to have relevant feedback before sending out the updated survey to the totality of the Service Providers. It can be added that the TCS have already been informed about the upcoming surveys. It has been decided to carry out the surveys online, using the technical resources of UiB (8.1 Task leader). Another practical issue was raised at the meeting of the Executive Board on July 7th 2020, regarding the fact that several WPs plan to launch surveys with the same stakeholders as tasks 2.2 and 8.1, although on other subjects. In order to avoid multiple surveys being sent out in a short time, causing confusion and potentially decreasing the reply rate, it has been decided that the EPOS ERIC Management Office should coordinate the surveys. The Service Provider and Data Provider surveys should take place at the beginning of 2021.

3. Data Protection

While no research data properly speaking are managed within the Landscape Analysis, the personal data protection notion needs to be taken into account while managing interviews and surveys. The leaders of the concerned tasks, CNRS (Task 2.2) and UiB (Task 8.1), will bear the responsibility for data management, with supervision and validation from EPOS ERIC. CNRS and UiB, as research institutions, have their own policies and standards for treating personal and other data. This creates a guarantee for appropriate management of the outcomes of the interviews and the surveys. Indeed, the Executive Coordination Office (ECO) has underlined the importance of data protection and it has issued recommendations to tackle these matters at project level. For example, all surveys that are carried out within EPOS SP should be reported to ECO. Within EPOS SP, WP9, led by EPOS ERIC, is responsible for ethical issues, including data protection. However, the two reports that they are expected to deliver will not be ready until mid-project (June 2021).

The interest of using tools as interviews and surveys for the Landscape Analysis cannot be questioned but there is however a need for caution while preparing them and while treating the collected information. At this stage, it seems that the only personal data that will be collected, are the names, positions and email addresses of the people interviewed and surveyed. These data will not be made public and will be shared mainly within the work groups of the two tasks and at most within the EPOS SP project. When choosing technical solutions for the online surveys, data protection will be considered. Finally, participants will be informed about the collection and management of data.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable D2.3 describes the methodology and provides guidelines for performing the Landscape Analysis as a key activity coordinated by WP2 and, to some extent, by WP8. The methodology concerns the actions to be undertaken to collect information from selected stakeholders and the guidelines present the approach and the timeline. The Landscape Analysis concerns the mapping and description of the EPOS Delivery framework considered as a multidimensional space in which each dimension corresponds to a specific element determining the construction and the operation of the EPOS RI. The Landscape Analysis is focused on the internal structure of the EPOS RI and it is aimed at understanding its functioning for creating awareness about the sustainable operation of the EPOS Delivery Framework. It can be considered as a sort of organisational analysis of the mission-driven EPOS RI. The Landscape Analysis itself represents a deliverable of the EPOS SP project to be produced at M30 (July 2022).

The Landscape Analysis is a dynamic undertaking and it will be performed in subsequent actions in a two-year's time span (July 2020 – July 2022). According to the methodological approach described in this document, the landscape of the EPOS Delivery Framework is composed of seven dimensions, being considered as the key elements of the EPOS RI operation:

1. Governance
2. Financial
3. Legal
4. Technological
5. Users' environment
6. Stakeholders' environment (private sector, society)
7. Global connections.

The initial conditions to start the Landscape Analysis, first action, will concern the analysis of existing documents elaborated during the EPOS IP project and delivered to EPOS ERIC and on further documentation elaborated after the conclusion of the EPOS IP project by the EPOS community.

The second action has a short-term perspective and it will be conducted in 2020. It will consist of two rounds of interviews with the TCS and the ICS: the first in July-August 2020 and the second in September-October 2020. This action will focus on the first four dimensions of the landscape, namely governance, legal, financial and technical dimensions. They represent the practical realisation of the sustainability actions. These four key elements are not independent of each other, but intrinsically connected and the Landscape Analysis has to be undertaken considering their mutual relationships. The interviews will update the scenario depicted by the existing documents and it will better address the gathered information.

The third action still has a short-term perspective and it concerns interactions with National Authorities through the EPOS ERIC General Assembly (GA) and the National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB). This action will start in September 2020 and it will be performed routinely during the two years to discuss the architecture and the organisational asset allowing EPOS ERIC guiding the EPOS Delivery Framework.

The second and third actions will address governance and financial aspects, with a particular attention to the updating of the TCS Cost-Book, the mapping through shared procedures of the in-kind contributions to further support the data and service provision and the completion of the EPOS ERIC governance model

through the signature of Collaboration and Framework Agreements to formally establish the TCS and finalise the hosting and the operation of the ICS-C.

The main goal of the short-term landscape analysis is to map and describe the four key dimensions of relevance for the long-term sustainability: namely, the governance, legal, financial and technical dimensions. This will allow EPOS ERIC to perform a first analysis of the financial viability, of the robustness of the governance model and of the readiness of the legal and technical dimensions. The EPOS SP project has been designed for this undertaking and WP2 and WP8 have been equipped with the necessary skills and experience. Furthermore, the activity plan of the EPOS SP project is a key element of the sustainability analysis of the EPOS Delivery Framework included in the 2020-2022 EPOS ERIC Strategic Plan.

The fourth action will consist of a further interaction with the “enlarged” EPOS community and it will be conducted through surveys using dedicated questionnaires. This action is considered a mid- to long-term activity. It will start in 2021 and it will address all dimensions of the EPOS delivery landscape. For this reason, it is expected that also the other WPs of the EPOS SP project (namely, WP3, 4, 5 and 6) will be involved to contribute exploring the users’ and stakeholders’ environments as well as the global dimension of the EPOS RI. A second round of TCS interviews in September-October 2020 will also be essential to get a first, general view on the long-term sustainability perspective. The first survey will concern the data and service provision as described above (section 2.4).

The landscape analysis of the EPOS Delivery Framework will provide content to other deliverables envisioned in WP2 and WP8, such as those related with the EPOS ERIC financial plan and D8.5 *EPOS Long-term Sustainability Plan*. EPOS SP project also through the Landscape Analysis will provide the key findings for the design of a sustainable operational phase from 2022 onward corroborating the long term perspective.

The design and the planning of the Landscape Analysis will be discussed with other European RI in order to contribute to the implementation and the adoption of good practices for managing and operating distributed research infrastructures worldwide. The present guidelines and the final report on the Landscape Analysis are public documents.

Annex 1 - TCS Interview Guidelines (July 2020)

Guidelines for TCS interviews 2020

EPOS-SP WP2 & 8

2020-07-13

WP2 and WP8 members (CNRS, UiB, EPOS-ERIC, ETH and GFZ) will carry out interviews with the TCS in July/August and September/October 2020. The interviews will take the form of teleconferences and last around 2 hours.

Context

Interviews will be conducted in the framework of EPOS-SP and concern project tasks 2.2, 2.3 and 8.1. The main objective is to collect information in view of the updating of financial data, to improve our understanding of the current services status, as well as to get input to the long-term vision of service operation. Consideration of legal, governance, financial and technical aspects of this is of utmost importance to draft the EPOS sustainability plan, which is the overarching goal of EPOS-SP WP8.

More specifically, interviews are planned in the context of the activation of the Governance & Coordination services through Collaboration Agreements in 2020, as well as the discussion on financial eligibility for 2021-2023 framework agreements that will be approved in the fall 2020. The EPOS ERIC General Assembly has approved the activation of the service for TCS Governance and Coordination during the last meeting in June 2020. An exchange with the TCS is thus necessary, to understand the current TCS governance structure, work-plan of activities in 2020 and 2021-2023 respectively, and the financial status.

Finally, the interviews will integrate the existing information collected from existing documents (mainly elaborated at the end of the EPOS IP project in 2019) and used to perform a Landscape Analysis, as envisioned in the EPOS SP project. The objective of the Landscape Analysis is to imagine, map and describe the multidimensional space characterizing the EPOS Delivery Framework. The Deliverable D2.3 envisioned in WP2 of the EPOS SP project describes the guidelines for the Landscape Analysis and includes the TCS interviews as a key element of the adopted methodology.

Expected participants

- TCS Boards: SCC member + Chair of Consortium Board (if not the same) + as many members as possible of the TCS board members and service providers.

Short-term objectives

- **TCS Architecture:**
 - TCS Coordinator (service provider for TCS Governance & Coordination)
 - Confirmation of Service Providers as declared in the in TCS Cost-book in EPOS-IP
 - TCS Board composition and implementation status
 - External boards foreseen and established
- **Establishment of the TCS Governance & Coordination in 2020:**
 - Elaboration of the Collaboration Agreements for TCS Gov. & Coord. in 2020
 - Work-plan for the TCS Governance & Coordination activities in 2020 (incl. outreach)
 - Confirmation of the Service Provider, TCS Coordinator, (one expected per TCS)
 - Financial support for 2020

- Roadmap to finalize and sign the Collaboration Agreements in 2020
- **Outreach activities in 2020 potentially funded by EPOS ERIC.**
- **Data provision:**
 - Confirmation of Service Providers as declared in the in TCS Cost-book in EPOS-IP
 - Confirmation of DDSS under each service (structure of data providers)
 - List of contacts per Service Provider (scientific, technical, legal/financial)
 - Schedule for beginning of operations (readiness)
- **Sharing a roadmap to update financial information:**
 - Shared approach to update the TCS Cost Book
 - Discussion on EPOS-ERIC cash contribution + in-kind support (confirmation of the estimated amounts in the cost-book, funding sources, level of commitment for 2021-2023).
 - Financial viability for service provision: In-kind resources vs In-kind contributions.
 - List of validated services, eventually ready to enter the EPOS Pilot operational phase in 2021 with no additional funds required from EPOS-ERIC for 2021.
- **Landscape Analysis: methodological aspects:**
 - Approaches to map and describe each dimension of the landscape:
 - Governance
 - Legal
 - Financial
 - Technical
 - Users' and Stakeholders' environments
 - Global Dimension.
 - Roadmap: workflow and timeline.

Medium-term objectives

- **Elaboration of the TCS Governance & Coordination Framework Agreement for 2021-2023:**
 - Work-plan for the TCS Governance & Coordination activities in 2021-2023
 - Discussion on the governance structure and the number of Service Providers
 - Updating of costs declared in the TCS Cost-book in EPOS-IP
 - Timetable
- **Sharing the contributions to the Landscape Analysis to be done in EPOS SP**, contributing to the work on long-term sustainability (financial and governance dimensions of the analysis).
- **Base for design of online surveys** to go out later in the year to service and data providers in the framework of EPOS-SP work on long-term sustainability. Relevant questions:
 - Level of sustainability from data providers: identification of key data providers
 - Main risks associated to service provision
 - Ways in which EPOS can help Service Providers and Data Providers to sustain service provision at national/regional level
 - Specific aspects identified by TCS/Service Providers to ensure long-term sustainability of EPOS services.